

Scoping document

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Introduction

The EU mission: a soil deal for Europe, defines “improve soil structure” as one of the 8 mission objectives, addressing the importance to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops. Soil structure really makes soil what is and is a key factor in leading to the functioning of soil. Soil structure is vital for many processes in soil: how air and water and nutrients can move, provides aeration to plants and microbes, and helps to resist soil erosion and compaction, and is therefore linked to plant growth and it also supports the ecosystems services of the soil (Rabot et al. 2018). Soils structure has been defined as “spatial arrangement of solids and pores at scales smaller than the soil horizon, and consists of clusters of solids and pores called aggregates, that have hierarchical, emergent properties, and memory that define their functions” (Yudina and Kuzyakov 2023). The arrangement of the particles, aggregates, and voids determine the capacity of soil to transmit solutes and oxygen through the soil volume, and to retain and provide substances such as nutrients. Recently there has been a debate on different perspectives on soil structure. The two main viewpoints have been called ‘aggregate perspective’ and ‘pore perspective’, linking mainly to the usefulness of the concept of aggregates in different contexts (Roosch 2024). Intensification of land management is a key driver of soil structural deterioration (Keller et al. 2019, Klöffel et al. 2024). Increasing weight of the machinery used in agriculture and in forestry poses a threat to soil pore system through

compaction causing changes in pore volume, pore-size distribution, and connectivity. Similarly, intensive tillage is related to reduced aggregate stability and increased risk for surface sealing and erosion (Bronick and Lal 2005). These management-induced changes in soil pore system affect water and gas movement in soil (e.g. Strömberg et al. 2016) and therefore also the living environment of soil biota and plant roots (Oades 1993). When changes in aggregate stability and pore system lead to reduced soil productivity, the input of carbon (C) through decaying plant materials as well as exudates and debris of soil biota (Costa et al. 2018) as well as soil necromass is also reduced leading to decreasing organic carbon (OC) content in soil. Lower SOC content is related to lower aggregate stability (Six et al. 2000, Soenneke et al. 2016) thus enhancing further the risk for structural deterioration. Furthermore, climate change puts the soil structure on stress through extreme weather conditions. Extreme rain events lead also to changes in pore structure which maintains the healthy soil. Draught has been shown to decrease carbon accumulation to soils. We do not know what happens to soil structure when these extreme weather events follow each other repeatedly. There should be critical analysis of some emergency measures currently adopted in the post-forest fire phase, such as emergency stabilization or aerial seeding.

State-of-the-Art

Soil is healthy when it is in good chemical, biological and physical condition and can continuously provide as many ecosystem services (such as safe, nutritious and sufficient food, biomass, clean water, nutrients cycling, carbon storage and a habitat for biodiversity) as possible. How can we then define what is a good soil structure? One of the most important indicators is how soil structure is connected to the soil water retention and gas exchange. Water retention is responsible for life on Earth as we know it. It allows for a huge air-water interface which permits aquatic aerobic activity to proceed under a range of environmental conditions. This activity underpins many global biogeochemical cycles. While we can destroy soil structure with, for example intensive and wrongly timed soil tillage and forest management practices and excessive handling of soil but we can also preserve soil structure. Regenerative agriculture practices (e.g holistic grazing, catch crop, cover crop and crop rotation among others) provide an option for the intensive management practices. But can we improve/regenerate destroyed soil structure? The growing interest on reduced tillage and carbon farming have potential to improve aggregate structure but improving the growth conditions of roots and enabling proper water and gas movement deeper in the soil would require loosening the soil structure at least down to the desired root penetration depth. No-till management known to improve soil aggregate stability may, depending on climate and soil type, enhance soil compaction and therefore slowly lead to lower productivity. On the other hand, reduced disturbance of soil improves the living conditions of soil fauna and therefore may have positive effect on soil macroporosity.

Knowledge Gaps

But with soil being diverse, what is the best structure? Or, should we define the structural quality of soils according to their resilience to climatic disturbances, such as varying weather conditions, filed traffic/ forest machinery and/or management practices such as tillage. Or should the optimal structure be connected to water retention and filtration capacity to support primary production and to secure clean water sources or to habitat provision for biodiversity contributing to biodiversity conservation and pest and disease control? And how we can take into account the relative importance of these different ecosystem services provided by soil structure in different pedoclimatic zones, soil types and land-use types.? Soils and their structure can change, and we need more information on ecosystems that undergo change such as thawing permafrost or restored soils such as peat? Last, how to get the info on best practices to the actors when they are so diverse group?

How to measure soil structure

Assessing the soil structure holds a great variety of analysis methods, each of them emphasizing different aspects of soil structure and possibly being suitable for only certain kind of soils. Methods may also be suitable only in the field, in monoliths or only in the laboratory, or only for the intact or homogenized soils. Some methods are cheap and widely applicable in context with the field sampling, and utilized for example in the current European-wide field studies and surveys, but less informative and difficult to be interpreted, while certain new methods are informative but expensive and need rare equipment. Approach may be in measuring soil water with methods such as water retention, infiltration, water holding capacity, field capacity or hydraulic conductivity, in measuring traditional soil features as bulk density, air permeability, and rooting, or more detailed structures as aggregate formation, size distribution and stability. Nevertheless, combination of new technologies such as nanoscale geophysics, tomography, spectrometry or single-cell genomics (Hartmann and Six 2022, Romero-Ruiz et al. 2018) to Sentinel or other satellite-derived data are probably needed to bridge the still existing knowledge gaps between soil management, structural features as pore structure and connectivity and soil functioning.

Land management

Abrupt land-use changes from forest to arable land, natural disturbances (forest fires) and tillage practices modify soil structure affecting soil functions and soil resilience. Use of heavy machinery may lead to soil compaction affecting soil functions like water regulation and retention, habitat provision and therefore ability of soil to provide ecosystem services such as primary production. Compaction and reduced plant growth can lead to increased runoff of nutrients and carbon, and reduced drought tolerance. Compaction may cause problems for soil organisms and their function (Meurer et al. 2020). For example, their biological activity may decrease affecting the decomposition of soil organic matter, maintenance of soil structure (exopolysaccharides, glomalin, fungal hyphae). The emerging issue of microplastics in European soils is conceptually also a physical

contaminant and affects soil aggregation and pore-size distribution (Wang et al. 2023, Han et al. 2024). However, the impact is likely to fluctuate based on the textural composition of the soil, as well as the size, shape, and aging characteristics of the microplastics particles (Lehmann et al. 2021, Wang et al. 2022). The change in management or caused by natural disturbances may lead to new structural state in soil or the change may be short-lived and there will be a reversion to the pre-disturbance state. The consequences of these changes in land management or changes resulting from natural disturbances, and the rates of these changes may differ depending on climate, soil and vegetation cover, management, and disturbance history. Therefore, more information is needed on specific management practices in different climatic environments and soil types that consider the land-use and functioning of the soil for provision of as many as possible ecosystem services. The improvement of soil structural quality can be assessed by physical-structural-hydrological parameters (aggregate stability, MWD, pF-curves, bulk density) linked to soil microbiology (at least, Microbial carbon, Basal soil respiration, Enzyme activity). There is a gap that should be explored between soil physical-structural and biological builders of soil structure. A particular challenge is that in many cases soil in poor condition is not responsive to management practices as it should.

Soil operations affect the soil structure, but with optimal timing the destabilizing effect can be reduced. For example, soil wetness and inherent soil properties contribute to soil structural vulnerability and their interaction is complicated depending also on the management practices (Hu et al. 2023). Minimum tillage has been considered the best approach from numerous biological points of views such as symbiotic fungi and arthropods, although this might not necessarily be the case with increasing number of weeds and reduction in yield levels. We need information on soil specific management options in different climatic conditions and land-use systems to improve the functionality of soil structure.

Aggregates

Soil aggregates are considered for hot spots for biological activity and biogeochemical processes and are of high importance defining soil structure and pore space. However, the efficacy of aggregate research in elucidating functioning of soil structure has come under scrutiny. Sampling aggregates has required disrupting the surrounding soil environment, raising concerns that aggregates may partially result from the sampling procedure, thus potentially compromising their representativeness (Young et al. 2001, Garland et al. 2023). Furthermore, non-destructive imaging techniques have failed to detect aggregates in undisturbed soils or in deeper soil layers (Garland et al. 2023). Recently, Garland et al (Garland et al. 2023) concluded that aggregates can be separate units but taking into account the processes contributing to the formation and turnover of aggregates, they don't need to have distinct physical boundaries. In fact, tillage-produced aggregates are often loosely packed and form inter-fragment spaces whereas natural aggregates are more likely to be seamlessly embedded in the surrounding soil matrix (Or et al. 2021). Yudina and Kuzyakov (Yudina and Kuzyakov 2023) stated that they "consider the pores and the interfaces as the arena of the physico-chemical and biological processes, but aggregates

as the result of these processes". Consequently, aggregates ensoul the concept of stable pedogenic features (soil memory) and allow to realize a thermodynamic view on the soil structure. This further highlights the importance of understanding aggregation and developing methods to study aggregates in their functional surrounding. From a biological perspective the pore network is highly pertinent as it is the habitable space for microbial species.

The cementing agents that enhance aggregate formation are well-known and natural aggregates are formed as a result of biological activity resulting in stabilization by biopolymers, and mineral particle enmeshing by hyphae and roots. Small and fine roots produce optimal conditions to form and to stabilize aggregates due to the polysaccharides produced by the microorganisms (Hallett et al. 2022). Furthermore, the roots maintain the aggregates mechanically separated. However, tillage produces soil fragments similar to biologically formed aggregates, but the stability of the fragments against mechanical disturbance and wetting is lower (Or et al. 2021). More information is needed how these differently formed aggregates impact the functioning of arable and natural soils and what is the relative importance of these different types of aggregates in preserving soil organic carbon stocks in different soil types and in soils under different land-use and management. Small sized aggregates seem to improve soil hydrological properties like water retention capacity and infiltration, so the estimation of this fraction or derived indexes or ratios, which relate the percentage of micro to macroaggregates, can give an interesting information about the condition and degradation of Mediterranean soils.

Weather events

Machado et al. 2018

With **changes in weather events and in annual timing of them**, there is a transition in timing of the soil management practices at both forest soils, agricultural soils and in the urban areas. When the soil is too moist, for example for the lack of frost period due to milder winters, certain machinery cannot be used without causing dramatic effects to the soil structure. Thus, the proper winter in Northern Europe with frost period protects soils from damage and allows use of heavy machinery (in forests). In addition, frost and the freeze thaw cycles are known to improve structure in arable soils by maintaining a good distribution of aggregate size. Unfortunately, currently climate change appears as milder temperature and increased precipitation in winter period, leading to greater leaching of organic material from the soils. Increased occurrence of heavy rain is possible also in more Southern regions, and thereby the concern of the loss of soil organic matter and soil structural changes is global. Abnormal weather events make trees susceptible to forest diseases, and in turn, loss of trees alter soil stability. In addition, the possibility for increased leaching is not restricted only to organic matter but may concern also particulate material (suspended solids) as well as nutrients essential for e.g. forest ecosystems in the long run. (Machado et al., 2018b)

Biotic part of soils

On forest land there is a growing interest among landowners towards sc. continuous cover forestry, where one avoids clear-cuts and site preparations. If continuous cover forestry practices get more common and grow in area that results a significant change by reducing the need for soil preparation and for maintenance ditching on drained peatlands. Different harvesting practices may also have a variable effect on the forest soil structure and nutrient amounts remaining in the site after cuttings. If cutting covers all tree compartments (whole-tree harvesting), this increases the loss of organic matter and nutrients compared to that remaining in the soil in stem-only harvesting. The distribution of logging residue piles on the site may also affect soil structure (physical properties) and nutrition (organic matter, chemical properties), i.e. if the logging residues are located only on restricted parts in the harvested area due to modern harvesting techniques. In addition to physical soil management, human induced land use include change in plant species, particularly in agriculture but to certain extent also in forest systems. The narrowing of plant species selection has further extended to genetic diversity via the use of breeding of plant material often to maximize productivity. Plant breeding has changed root exudates, root microbes, soil chemistry via microbes, lack of arbuscular mycorrhiza, glomalins and other extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) thus affecting the soil structure.

We need information, not just on agricultural soils, but on the physico-chemical processes, all the biological processes and interactions, from larger plants and animals to fungal hyphae and tiny microbes. How soil organisms interact with each other and with the abiotic environment affects soil structure. The effect of soil invertebrates has been neglected for crop production. The biotic part maintains the structure, how is it affected by climate change and changes in the soil habitat? How do soil animals and microbes respond to extreme events? In addition, the role of microbes in the presence and absence of OM may be different and should be understood.

Biodiversity crisis and the change in biodiversity can have an effect on the extracellular polymeric substances produced by microbes and thus have a strong effect on soil structure. In forests, the forest stand age and management can affect the resilience of soil to draught and heat waves, and on how the soil responds to the drought. In addition, the different management practices bring along forest floor vegetation changes mediating the effects of drought on soil. One example are the forest fires in Portugal which are a major threat affecting soil structural, soil biota, soil physico-chemical with also off-site effects (flooding, ash deposition in damns, ...). Besides that, forest management practices affect soil structural properties (timber extraction, land preparation by terraces, and so on), forest fires themselves modify environment, being a major threat.

Last knowledge gap is associated to the recovery of soil after disturbances, which is tightly linked to soil structure. We do not know how long it takes for soil to recover and also how do we measure soil recovery. The anthropogenic effects have a major role in shaping soil structure, but we do not have a complete and soil- and climate-specific understanding on their direct impacts on soil structure and how to retain sustainability of soil after disturbance. The potentially important role of plants in restoration needs also more soil and

management specific understanding. Furthermore, as the functioning of soil results from an interplay of soil structure and activity of soil organisms, recovery of the vast areas of deteriorated soils on earth is a challenge.

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